

Upadacitinib silences IL1b.

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We report here silencing of interleukin 1-beta by the chemical inhibitor of the Janus kinase JAK1 upadacitinib (Rinvoq). Thus, in a myeloid cell type that expressed the inflammatory cytokine IL-1b, a selective Jak1 inhibitor was able to silence it.

Citations

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